

Research Article

Mathematical Model for the Control of Cholera Disease with Vaccination and Treatment Strategies: A Direct Mode of Transmission Approach

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Abstract

Cholera is waterborne diseases caused by vibrocholerae which can be transmitted directly from human to human or via contaminated channels. In this paper, we proposed a mathematical model for the control of cholera diseases with vaccination and treatment strategies considering only the direct mode of transmission. The total population N was partitioned into four epidemiological groups and the local stability of a disease free equilibrium and an endemic equilibrium were analysed. We obtained Routh-Hurwitz necessary and sufficient conditions for local asymptotic stability. The numeral simulation is investigated to enable us to visualise the effects of vaccine and treatment and the results reveal that with improved treatment, high quality sanitary healthcare and the use of oral rehydration therapy (ORT) for the patients eradicate the spread of cholera in the population.

Keywords cholera, vaccination, treatment, direct mode, basic reproduction number.

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Introduction

Cholera is a severe infection of the small intestine caused by *bacterium vibriocholerae* (Inkelstein, 2017), (Nabede *et al.*, 2012). It is a highly contagious disease caused by the organism which contaminates water, food, drinks, which, when swallowed through any of these channels disorganise normal activities in the small intestine, which leads to constant vomiting, stooling loss of weight and severe feverish condition (Oworu *et al.*, 2010). Cholera can be transmitted in two ways, namely, indirectly to human through contaminated water or food or directly from human to human in a homosexual population (Pauline, 2017). Cholera is an acute intestinal infectious disease caused by the *bacterium vibriocholerae* which, result in extreme diarrhoea and vomiting and stooling. It is a deadly communicable disease which usually occurs from untreated water and from the unfavourable hygienic condition and sanitation, it causes loss of water in the human body and hinders from absorbing liquids (Pauline, 2017). The sign and symptoms of cholera include, dehydration leg cramps, low blood pressure, loss of appetite, severe feverish condition (McElroy and Townsend, 2009). Cholera origin is traced to the German bacteriologist, Robert Koch (1843-1910), who studied the disease during an epidemic in Egypt. He found bacterium in the intestine of those who had died of cholera, but could neither isolate the organism nor infect animals with it (Kraft, 2018). Despite easy treatment of cholera, its estimated to affect between 3 and 5 million people each year, and it causes over 100,000 deaths worldwide (Kraft, 2018). Mathematical model enable us to investigate the general and specific behaviour of system of equation analytically and to understand the sensitivity of some threshold parameters in order to provide preventive measures and control strategies. The application of differential equation in the spread analysis of infectious disease have been extensively used by several researchers, the results of this model analyses predicted and suggested several control techniques for the control and the estimation of the infectious diseases (Dontwi *et al.*, 2014; Ahmed *et al.*, 2013; Ochoche, 2015; Wang and Modnak, 2011). Tian *et al.* (2013) in extension of Codeco's proposed general model which considers the different infective states of *V. cholera*, consisting of three differential equations which describe the relationship between the susceptible (S), infectious (I) and removed individuals (R) the dynamics of the hyper infective states of the population of *vibriocholera* where the total population is assumed to be N, is constant. Misra and Singh (2014), proposed a modification to the existing cholera model considering the density of the pathogen for the infected human in the population, taking his fact from the relationship between the human environment

and the population of the *vibroscholera* in contaminated water. Andam *et al.* (2015) designed mathematical models to study transmission dynamics and control of the disease. Diekmann *et al.* (1990) studied modelling cholera dynamics with a control strategy in Ghana, using these compartments, the susceptible individuals at time t $S(t)$, infected individuals, at time t $I(t)$ the recovered individuals at the time t $R(t)$, and $C(t)$ the *vibrio cholera* concentration in the water supply at time t .

Model Formulation

Model assumption was developed under the following assumptions.

- Only direct mode of transmission is considered
- Disease induced death rate occurs only in the infected class due to effective treatment
- Age, social status, race and sex do not affect the rate of infection
- There is no migration and emigration
- When vaccine failure occurs vaccinated individuals can be susceptible
- The recruited humans are previously uninfected

Model Description

The total population N is grouped into four epidemiological sub population via, vaccinated humans (V), susceptible humans (S), infected humans (I) and recovered humans (R).

A vaccinated individual becomes susceptible through the rate of α_2 due to vaccine failure, a susceptible individual becomes vaccinated through the rate α_3 . α_8 is the recruitment rate, a susceptible through the rate α_4 , α_5 is the recovery rate. The recovered individuals become susceptible at the rate α_6 . α_1 and α_2 are the natural death rate and disease induced death rate respectively. Table 1 shows the descriptions of the parameters.

Definitions of Variables and Parameters used in the Model

Table 1: Variables / Parameters Descriptions

Variable / Parameter	Description
V	Number of vaccinated individuals at time t
S	Number of susceptible individuals at time t
I	Number of infected individuals at time t
R	Number of recovered individuals at time t
μ	Natural death rate
α_1	Rate of vaccine failure
α_2	Rate of vaccination
β_1	Rate at which susceptible humans become infected
γ	Recovery rate
α_3	Rate at which recovered individuals become susceptible
μ_1	Disease induced death rate
α_4	The recruitment rate
$N(t)$	Total population

Figure 1: Schematic Diagram for the Model

From the above definition and assumptions we formulate the following non – linear ordinary differential equations

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = \alpha_3 S - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)V \quad 1$$

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \alpha_8 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_6 R - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4)S \quad 2$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = \alpha_4 S - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)I \quad 3$$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \alpha_5 I - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_6)R \quad 4$$

Subject to initial conditions

$$V(0) > 0, S(0) > 0, I(0) > 0, R(0) > 0$$

$$N(t) = V(t) + S(t) + I(t) + R(t) \tag{5}$$

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = \alpha_8 + \alpha_1 S - \alpha_1 V - \alpha_1 I - \alpha_7 I + \alpha_5 I - \alpha_1 R \tag{6}$$

INVARIANT REGION

Theorem 1

The solutions of the model equations are feasible for all $t > 0$ if they entire invariant region Ω

Proof

Let $\Omega = (V, S, T, R) \in R_+^4$ be any solution of the model equations with initial conditions described above.

Given that there is no disease induced death rate equation (6) reduces to

$$\frac{dN}{dt} \leq \alpha_8 - \alpha_1 N \tag{7}$$

$$\frac{dN}{dt} + \alpha_1 N \leq \alpha_8$$

From integrating factor method

$$I.F = e^{\int \alpha_1 dt} = e^{\alpha_1 t}$$

$$e^{\alpha_1 t} \frac{dN}{dt} + \alpha_1 N e^{\alpha_1 t} \leq \alpha_8 e^{\alpha_1 t}$$

$$\frac{dN}{dt} (N e^{\alpha_1 t}) \leq \alpha_8 e^{\alpha_1 t}$$

$$d(N e^{\alpha_1 t}) \leq \alpha_8 e^{\alpha_1 t} dt$$

Integrate both sides we have

$$N e^{\alpha_1 t} \leq \frac{\alpha_8}{\alpha_1} e^{\alpha_1 t} + k_0$$

Multiply through by $e^{-\alpha_1 t}$

$$N(t) \leq \frac{\alpha_8}{\alpha_1} + k_0 e^{-\alpha_1 t}$$

Applying the initial condition $t(0) = N(0)$

Suppose $V(0) > 0, S(0) > 0, I(0) > 0, R(0) > 0$

Then the solutions (V, S, I, R) of the model equations are positive for all $t > 0$

Proof

From equation 1

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = \alpha_3 S - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)V \leq -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)V \quad 8$$

$$\frac{dV}{dt} \leq -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)V$$

Integrate and apply $V(0) = 0$

$$V(0) \leq k_0$$

$$V(t) \leq V(0)e^{-(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)t} \quad 9$$

From equation 2

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \alpha_8 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_6 R - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4)S \leq -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4)S \quad 10$$

$$\frac{dS}{dt} \leq -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4)S$$

Integrating and applying the initial conditions

$$S(0) \leq k_2$$

$$S(t) \leq S(0)e^{-(\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4)t} \quad 11$$

From equation 3

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = \alpha_4 S - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)I \leq -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)I \quad 12$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} \leq -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)I$$

Integrating and applying the initial conditions

$$I(0) \leq k_3$$

$$I(t) = I(0)e^{-(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)t} \tag{13}$$

From equation

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \alpha_5 I - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_6)R \leq -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_6)R$$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} \leq -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_6)R$$

Integrating and applying the initial conditions

$$R(0) \leq k_4$$

$$R(t) = R(0)e^{-(\alpha_1 + \alpha_6)t} \tag{14}$$

Therefore it has been proved that all the solutions of the model equations are positive for any $t > 0$

Model Analysis

Deterministic differential equations will be analysed qualitatively in order to determine the conditions for existence local stability and stability of disease free equilibrium points (Inkelstein, 2017) the above analysis enables us to investigate the impact of vaccination and treatment of cholera disease in a population.

Equilibrium State

At equilibrium point

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = \frac{dS}{dt} = \frac{dI}{dt} = \frac{dR}{dt} = 0$$

$$\frac{dV}{dt} \alpha_3 S - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)V = 0 \tag{15}$$

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \alpha_8 + \alpha_2 v + \alpha_6 R - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4)S = 0 \tag{16}$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = \alpha_4 S - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)I = 0 \tag{17}$$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \alpha_5 I - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_6)R = 0 \tag{18}$$

Disease free equilibrium state of the model

At disease free equilibrium the entire compartment with element of infection with zero it implies that $I^* = 0, R^* = 0$ therefore we have

$$(V^*, S^*, I^*, R^*) = \left(\frac{\alpha_3 \alpha_8 (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)}{(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)[(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_4) - \alpha_2 \alpha_3]}, \frac{\alpha_8 (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)}{(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_4) - \alpha_2 \alpha_3}, 0, 0 \right)$$

Epidemic Equilibrium state of the model

From equation 15 to 18 we have

$$S^* = \frac{N(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)}{\alpha_9 \alpha_{10}}$$

$$V^* = \frac{\alpha_3 N(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)}{\alpha_9 \alpha_{10}(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)}$$

$$I^* = \frac{(\alpha_1 + \alpha_6)[(\alpha_1 + \alpha_6)(\alpha_1 N + \alpha_3 N) - \alpha_8 \alpha_9 \alpha_{10} - \alpha_2 \alpha_3 N]}{\alpha_5 (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)[\alpha_6 \alpha_9 \alpha_{10} N(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7) - \alpha_9 \alpha_{10} N(\alpha_1 + \alpha_6)]}$$

$$R^* = \frac{(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)(\alpha_1 N + \alpha_3 N) - \alpha_8 \alpha_9 \alpha_{10} - \alpha_2 \alpha_3 N}{(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)[\alpha_6 \alpha_9 \alpha_{10} N(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7) - \alpha_9 \alpha_{10} N(\alpha_1 + \alpha_6)]}$$

Basic Reproduction Number

For infectious disease model the basic reproduction number (R_0) can be defined as the effective number of secondary infections caused by infected human in the entire duration of infectiousness (Diekmann *et al.*, 1990). If (R_0) < 1, it signifies that on average an infected humans produces less than one new infected individual in duration of infectious and the infection can be eradicated from the population. Conversely, if (R_0) > 1, it implies that any infected human produces on average more than one new infection, and the disease will invade the population before tending to zero.

From equation 17 we have

$$\frac{dI}{dt} \frac{\alpha_9 \alpha_{10} I S_0}{N} - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_7) I = 0$$

$$R_0 = \frac{\alpha_9 \alpha_{10} S_0}{N(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)}$$

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Where $S_0 = S^*$

Local stability analysis of disease free equilibrium state

$$let M = \alpha_3 S - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)V \tag{A}$$

$$\frac{\partial m}{\partial I} = \frac{\partial m}{\partial R} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial m}{\partial S} = \alpha_3 \frac{\partial m}{\partial V} = -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)$$

$$N = \alpha_8 + \alpha_2 V \alpha_6 R - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4)S \tag{B}$$

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial V} = \alpha_2 \frac{\partial N}{\partial S} = -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4)$$

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial I} = 0 \quad \frac{\partial N}{\partial R} = \alpha_6$$

$$\rho = \alpha_4 S - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)I \tag{C}$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial V} = 0 \quad \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial S} = \alpha_4 \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial I} = -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial R} = 0$$

$$T = \alpha_5 I - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_6)R \tag{D}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial V} = 0 \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial S} = 0 \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial I} = \alpha_5 \frac{\partial T}{\partial R} = -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_6)$$

The Jacobian matrix is obtained as follows

$$y(\varepsilon f) = \begin{bmatrix} -((\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)) & \alpha_3 & 0 & 0 \\ \alpha_2 & -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4) & 0 & \alpha_6 \\ 0 & \alpha_4 & -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_5 & -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_6) \end{bmatrix}$$

The characteristic equations fields

$$|y(\varepsilon f) - \lambda I| = \begin{vmatrix} -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2) - \lambda & \alpha_3 & 0 & 0 \\ \alpha_2 & -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4) - \lambda & 0 & \alpha_6 \\ 0 & \alpha_4 & -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7) - \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_5 & -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_6) - \lambda \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\{-(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2) - \lambda\}\{-(\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4) - \lambda\}\{-(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7) - \lambda\}\{-(\alpha_1 + \alpha_6) - \lambda\} = 0$$

$$-(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2) - \lambda = 0 \text{ Or } -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4) - \lambda = 0 \text{ or } -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7) = 0 \text{ or } -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_6) - \lambda = 0$$

$$\lambda_1 = -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)\lambda_2 = -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4)\lambda_3 = -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)\lambda_4 = -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_6)$$

Since $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4 < 0$, it implies that the disease free equilibrium is Stable.

Stability Analysis of Non - Zero Equilibrium State.

The vital criterion by Routh - Hurwitz establish the necessary and sufficient conditions for all roots of the characteristics condition of the model with real coefficient to lie in the left half in complex plane.

The conditions are

- It is asymptotically stable if trace (J) < 0 and det(J) > 0
- It is stable but not asymptotically stable if trace (J) = 0 and det(J) > 0
- It is unstable if either trace (J) < 0 or det(J) > 0

$$let B = \begin{bmatrix} -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4) & 0 \\ \alpha_4 & -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7) \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore from matrix B, we have

$$Det(B) = -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4)(\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)$$

$$Trace(B) = -(\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4) - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)$$

$$= -[(\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4) + (\alpha_1 + \alpha_7)]$$

Since the $det(B) > 0$ and the $trace(B) < 0$ then we said that the model is locally asymptotically stable.

Numerical Simulations

Numerical simulation gives understanding the effects of every parameter used in the model and the control measures. The numerical simulation of our model was carried out with various set of parameters values in Table 2 using maple 18. It was discovered that at high treatment the rate at which people develop AIDS decreases monotonically.

Table 2. Initial conditions for each plot and parameters values.

Parameters and State Variables	Value	Source
S	9500	Assumed
I	500	Assumed
V	150	Assumed
R	3000	Assumed
α_3	0.01	(CDC, 2004)
N	13150	Calculated
α_1	0.25-0.75	Control parameter
α_2	0.25-0.85	Control parameter
α_5	0.08	Assumed
α_7	0.1	Assumed
α_8	0.0024	Calculated
α_6	0.2	Assumed
α_4	0.2	Assumed

Figure 2. The graph of susceptible individuals against time

Figure 2 is the graph of susceptible individuals against time, it can be seen from the graph that increase in vaccination rate decreases the susceptible individuals, that is to say vaccine is highly effective.

Figure 3. The graph of vaccinated individuals against time

Figure 3 shows the graph of vaccinated individuals against time, the graph shows that vaccination rate is directly proportional to vaccinated individuals.

Figure 4. The graph of Infectious individuals against time for different vaccination and treatment rates

Figure 4 is a graph of Infectious individuals against time for different vaccination and treatment rates. The graph shows that the populations of Infectious individuals decrease as vaccination and treatment rates.

Figure 5. The graph of recovered individuals against time for different vaccination and treatment rates.

Figure 5 is a graph of Recovered individuals against time for different vaccination and treatment rates. The graph shows that the population of Recovered individuals increases as vaccination and treatment rates.

Conclusion

This paper examines a vaccination epidemic model for the transmission dynamics of cholera considering only the direct mode of transmission. The local stability of disease free equilibrium was analysed and Routh-Hurwitz necessary conditions for locally asymptotic stability were obtained. Our result of basic reproduction number (R_0) shows that for $R_0 < 1$ the disease free equilibrium is locally stable which means that the disease decreases monotonically to zero

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